

5 Oct 1972.

Dear Barbara,

no problem
I shall
it is very

The application for Oman has gone off with the gent who is to deliver it to the proper authority (hopefully with an additional blessing). He seems to think it is all right.

You were described as Islamic scholar, Fellow of Oxford, director of 2 excavations + 1 survey, publications etc. You are also proclaimed as expedition epigraphist, and as such will please find out where I get LATEX in England. You are epigraphist + Islamic photographer, I am sure you or your technicians are required.

Whole outfit is under blessing of Peabody Museum. I'd have other backers I'd be glad to consider adding them.

Karen Friplatt is expected to be in Oman in early December and will be visited by Tosi. She has asked for £800 from Omanis. She order to avoid being squeezed out I arranged that I could be in Oman by Dec 1st if my man thought it necessary on getting back to Muscat. I know you said you were busy 'till Jan 1 but you could, if necessary, arrive a bit late and I'd rather not be preempted.

It is thought Karen Friplatt will work from Buraimi through Wadi Tiji to coast near present day Sohar. My man + I agreed that she probably had good rights ^{RIGHT} to the 44-2nd Mill BC in that area and I would have to look further south. However I told her that you + Tosi would want to follow your interests up in that area. These interests shouldn't conflict with Friplatt. So generally speaking the application was for all Oman, no boundaries specified, but Karen Friplatt probably has her rights in part of Oman with her 4-3rd Mill stuff.

~~As a last resort I supposed I can try to get the Economic~~
Adviser & override people & get us in.

The whole problem is not that they don't want us
or think we are respectable but solely that the Director
of Inf. thinks we will conflict with the Dames. God know
it's a big country and also $\frac{2}{3}$ of this outfit isn't even
interested in the same things. Anyhow I estimate we are
very very close to getting in. My friend has our visa info
and says he will process it as soon as he thinks air has
cleared. [There was some small misunderstanding betw
Air of Inf. and Economic Adviser but that is clearing up]

Anyhow I have informed my friend & the Ec. Adviser
that I'd like to arrive Muscat Dec. 27. I also said
that if necessary I could make it Dec 15th but ~~rather~~
I think the thing for me is to act as if Dec 27th was
and proceed on that basis. So I am setting up to cross
the channel on Dec 6th en route Muscat. Since you
are a thin builder and we may need some weighty
pushers of vehicles, I figured you could fly to Dubai
on Dec 26th, full of Christmas cheer, meet me there,
and it's not a very long drive to Muscat. Anyhow one
or two more days wouldn't matter as we could
Telegraph from Dubai or Abu Dhabi.

Unless I get a bland wall refusal before Dec 6th this
is what I'm going to do.

Therefore I and the Princess will be in England roughly about
November 22nd or 23rd staying with her parents in London
As regards getting this show on the road.

That was a good idea about survey instruments + L.K. I will speak to him about it.

For your own things, I gather the Ormani hills total mean army boots in a week [sharp rocks] therefore I suggest extra pairs of ^{heavy} shoes. If you like I can take the sort of thing in the car.

I leave it to you to get any inoculations you need.

I also gather it can be cool at night, and also we might get rained on.

My friend says we can get food in Muscat or out of oil company [By the way I gather the oil people are awfully nice with pleasure or at least interest. Some geologist want Judith to go over a lot dry like beds for shirts etc.] I think though we ought to take a certain amount of food, in the car from England, since the car goes anyway, and it would be better not to ~~rely~~ rely too much from the oil company rice, dates etc in the city I'm sure. I'd welcome suggestions on food. Also on what you personally refuse to eat or drink eg if you won't eat tuna fish, I'd like to know.

Paper pencils etc I think we should take from England. I am the owner of a bar compass now so I'll take that.

Coveris - I have 2 - 35s, Dwyer has 1 - 35s. Would you bring a Kallei. I will pay cleaning, insurance + libor.

Car - at the moment it has Dunlop RKB h/d road tires which will probably die for or they except mud and very bad sand. I didn't get English crosscountry tires cause I note Judith's didn't hold up very well. My friend in Muscat didn't see I think sand tires were needed where we're going I thought of getting the road direction military tires in Iran or at least two rear tires. Have you any thoughts on this?

~~now that~~ I think some of your clip top plaster bags might be useful but ordinary ones probably for general use. Have you any ideas on cloth bags?

Anything you would like in medicine, I leave things like personal malaria pills to you unless you rather I get them.

Do you want anything from Iran. I, I can save time by going Turkey, Syria, Iraq. but I am wary of the bloody Syrians, also a little bother about Iraq after BP's troubles. Anyhow I could do Iran if necessary and might anyhow - writing factor being snow, in the hills. I'm thinking of your motorbike mostly.

This is all I can think of right now, I kept a copy so know what I asked you & will ask more later.

I apologize deeply for changing dates like a 13 year old on her first date but I decided it was probably best to push on. by the Omanis are talking about having us come in April May by which time I think it's warm enough to make life a burden. & would suffice

Generally, I'd much appreciate any suggestions or advice. (Not that I promise to take it, but a miserable blogger as you know)

Hope all well with you.

Jim.

Prue's sends her best.